

Politics and Women in Nayantara Sahgal's *This Time of Morning*

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Abstract

Sahgal has portrayed the life of an Indian woman in our society. This Time of Morning seeks to explore the effects and outcome of political impacts as they work out in the life of persons, the seeking of identity that Indians craved for in these early years of independence and an identity based on an admixture of the best aspects of the west without separation of their own heritage is paralleled by Rashmi, Nita and Rakesh who themselves seek to express their own uniqueness and establish their own identity.

Keywords: freedom, self-respect, individuality, emancipation.

In *This Time of Morning*, the characters are of high positions. They are mostly politicians, influential bureaucrats, and artists, journalists with varied level of achievements, distinguished and noteworthy parliamentarians, emancipated, lustful and carnal society women and traditional, educated housewives. In *This Time of Morning*, the readers could find the glimpses of current history. The main characters of the novel are Kalyan Sinha, the minister without portfolio; Kailas, Prime Minister's trustworthy assistant brought up in the Gandhian congress Movement, Rakesh, a young I.F.S. officer; Sir Arjun Metra, the practical and rational secretary General of the Minister of External Affairs; Hari Mohan, a business man and Minister of Industries in the Government of Uttar Pradesh for a short span of time; Mira, the devoted and loyal wife of Kailas, Rashmi, the one and only daughter of Kailas and Mira; Nita, the daughter of the Narangs, a Newspaper columnist; and Uma is the beautiful wife of Arjun Mitra. The central theme of the novel is started by Rakesh who is the protagonist of the novel.

Sahgal has portrayed the life of an Indian woman in our society before marriage, through the character of Nita, she is the daughter of Dr. Narang and he is a combination of both Eastern and western culture. Dr. Narang as a man is very much enchanted towards western culture. But when it comes to his daughter Nita, he transforms himself into a traditional Indian who imposes the well-defined Indian norms for women and restrictions and limitations laid for women. But Nita as a highly ambitious woman could not bear and face all these restrictions laid on her. Dr. Narang has never allowed Nita to attend parties. She says: "We don't allow Nita to go out alone. Her father would not hear of it" (TM 30). Dr. Narang as a typical Indian father seems to be very much concerned with the safety and protection of his

daughter to abide by the traditional norms and values. Nita's parents do not allow her to smoke or drink or take part in club dances or attend parties till her marriage.

Sahgal condemns the typical Indian parent's mentality of having a strong hold on daughters till marriage and then wash off their hands on her after marriage. The Indian parents are not at all ready to pay heed or listen to the dreams, desires, wishes and aspirations that their daughters have in their gifted life. They aim only at finding a man of their option to give their daughter in marriage to him without worrying about her opinion on her marriage. Though Nita has reached the age of marriage, she is not ready to marry the man, her parents have chosen: "creatures her parents have in mind for her are either so awful or midgets or men who never open their mouth" (32). Nita is totally unhappy and feels uncomfortable when her parents exercise over powers on her to make her accept parents' decision to give her in marriage to a stranger. She accepts her parents' choice of Vijay as a groom, in spite of knowing his attitude towards her. Nita knows well that Vijay looks upon her as an object to be possessed. Nita knows very well that her marriage has no hope and possibility of fulfillment.

Due to the restrictions laid on her by her parents, Nita wants to break off those obstacles to see the world freely beyond them. Nita wants to live her own life according to her wish and she rejects the values and norms of the previous generation that are imposed upon her. Nita's search of her own real self is more stressed than the search of Rashmi. Because Nita has made may attempt to attain self-discovery even before marriage whereas Rashmi tries to do self-discovery only after her failure in marriage. Nita has her own principles and views on leading her life. They are absolutely different from what her dominating and conventional parents impose on her. She is fundamentally a fun loving girl. She enjoys going to clubs, to dance and to attend parties. She seems to be very much interested in smoking and drinking liquor.

Nita is a good actor and pretender before her parents. She is mostly kept in constraints and restrictions by her parents. But she gets a chance to move alone from her jail house and jailor parents, she behaves like a freed woman from a jail. Nayantara Sahgal in an article, "Women: Persons or Possessions?" writes that women are looked down upon as inanimate objects or property to be possessed. Sahgal aptly writes thus: "When I heard someone remark, we never allow daughters to go out," or "I can't do what my husband would not like it", it sounded a very peculiar alien jargon. As if, I thought women were property not persons" (IV).

Nita is a new woman who wishes to live her own life, with a job, earning her livelihood and leading a useful life. She resents an arranged marriage, which is overshadowed by material concerns where even sexual and emotional acts are merely conventional facades. (TM 45)

She chooses Kalyan as a man of her choice and submits herself to him. Nita is able to feel and find a peculiar comfort in his accompaniment. She tends to visit him frequently due to the comfort she finds in him. Once she refused to go home and frankly expressed her love for Kalyan.

"But don't make me go." He rose from his chair, "Nita..." She got up, too, and came like a sleep walker into his arms, clinging to him. "Don't make me go, please don't make me go." He took her by the hand and then to his room. (TM 152)

Nita's pre-marital relationship with Kalyan can be interpreted in three ways. It may be an attempt to fulfill her inner most desire. It may be an attempt to experience the love, care and concern from Kalyan which she couldn't feel in her father. Jasbir Jain expresses his opinion about Nita's sexual involvement with Kalyan thus:

With Kalyan Sinha, sex comes naturally to her not because he loves her but because she has unconsciously allowed herself to love and admire him and turn to him in her desperation at being hedged in by convention. (42)

Nita's yearning to get rid of the restrictions and limitations laid on her might have induced her go to the world that is freed of those limitations. Sahgal explores into the place of a woman in Indian society before marriage through the character of Nita. M. Selvanayagi writes:

Sahgal seems to expose conventional narrow-minded Indian society through the character of Nita. In Indian society, the parents choose life-partners. The parents arrange for the two young souls to live happily ever after. Sahgal strongly attacks this social convention and names this kind of marriage "just organized rape. (qtd: 274)

When the time has come to decide on her marriage, she stays passive and does not react or express her opinion to her parents because she is not expected of that. She has led her parents decide her future. Through the character of Nita, Sahgal clearly condemns the typical Indian Parents' mentality and their conventional narrow mindedness in choosing the life partners for their daughters without thinking about their opinion. The readers can see Nita moving towards self-awareness through unpredictability and bewilderment. Nita believes in arranged marriage as an institution while Kalyan Sinha views marriage as an act of barbarism. Nita does not seem to get attached with Kalyan Sinha in a realistic manner. Rather her deep and strong aspiration for self-discovery and self realisation has pulled her towards Kalyan Sinha. But she knows well that she is not her man. Dr.Kanupriya in her article "Feminist Consciousness in the novels of Nayantara Sahgal" analysed and presents her view:

In the character of Nita in *This Time of Morning* Sahgal explores the place of women in Indian society before marriage and the kind of freedom young women desire outside marriage. Sahgal refers to the rigid codes in a traditional society when a young girl reaches puberty, her movements are restricted, whereas marriage seems to be a license to do the things hitherto prohibited. Nita resents the idea of an arranged marriage. To her this kind of marriage does not offer any prospect of fulfillment. (47).

Women like Nita always look for self-satisfaction in whatever they do and seek for self-realization. So the readers can see some women perceiving marriage as freedom from parental restrictions according to the conventional norms and dominating and suppressing hold of the parents. Some consider marriage as a way to self-realization. As long as the patriarchal and conventional male defined norms and values exist in our country, there won't be any such thing as freedom of women and individuality of women. Moreover the women's dreams and hopes of attaining freedom, self-discovery and self-realization won't occur unless the patriarchal system is exiled from our country. Even the empowerment of women through education can't be successful unless the mothers who play the passive, fated and sacrificing roles in the family stop their pampering of sons and discouraging daughters. First of all, the senior women generation in the society should understand the value and power of the fellow women in the society and should start so stand in support of them to attain victory in the march of freedom, self-respect, individuality and emancipation

This Time of Morning provides an insight into the working of politics. On the other hand it seeks to explore the effects and outcome of these as they work out in the life of persons. Rakesh notices the disorder in his country and notes also the signs of progress. He realizes that the time has come to find an identity of their own as Indians of the new era-an identity based on a well judged mixture of modern ideas and ancient values. The seeking of identity that Indians craved for in these early years of independence and an identity based on an admixture of the best aspects of the west without separation of their own heritage is paralleled by Rashmi, Nita and Rakesh who themselves seeking to express their own uniqueness and establishing their own identity.

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